

DIRECTIONS OF EFFECTIVE USE OF DOMESTIC INVESTMENT POTENTIAL IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY

Ulichkina Lyudmila Ivanovna

**Tashkent institute of finance, teacher*

Email: [www. Ulichkina_l@mail.ru](http://www.Ulichkina_l@mail.ru)

Annotation: The article highlights the scientific foundations for the effective use of domestic investment potential in the national economy, provides a methodology for assessing the use of domestic investment, analyzes the effectiveness of capital, and provides recommendations for the effective use of domestic investment.

Key words: investment, domestic investment, accelerator model, marginal propensity to capital, efficient use of capital, efficient use of domestic investment.

Introduction

Investments are a necessary condition and source of ensuring the growth of the economy of any country, its comprehensive development. Accordingly, investment programs and regional investment programs are developed and implemented in our country every year in order to ensure the balanced development of various sectors and branches of the economy, to take into account the socio-economic potential of regions, and also to increase local employment. This makes it possible for the volume of investment in the economy to grow significantly from year to year and to give positive results by increasing the volume of national production.

Analysis of literature on the topic

The issues of effective use of investments in the national economy have been thoroughly studied by domestic and foreign economists. In particular, an economist from Uzbekistan D.K.Akhmedov cited the most important factors in

ensuring the active attraction of investments to our country, such as the availability of qualified personnel, sufficient data for analysis, increased interest of authorities in attracting investments, freedom of foreign trade, improvement of raw material supply [2].

A.A.Sadikov, the role of investment activity, which depends on the natural-economic, production, socio-demographic potential, is of particular importance in the socio-economic development of regions [3].

Russian scientist A. Damodaran, the experience of advanced foreign countries in investing in the national economy shows that arming production not with "heavy" technological lines, but with "flexible" production lines, which can be quickly updated and quickly adapt to market requirements, is becoming a priority. Investments are being directed not to cities with large industrial centers, but to regions with available raw materials and labor resources [4].

V.A.Kharitonov and A.O.Alekseev note that as a condition for the successful development of the national economy, it is necessary for business entities to work in a concerted manner in the field of investment and innovation [5].

G.I.Ivanov, investments in the regions of the country with high economic potential and rich in natural resources will increase the income of local budgets and provide an opportunity for sustainable development of the regions. Such a policy is effective both from the economic and social point of view. Therefore, the main task for the regions is to increase their investment opportunities, to effectively use the existing internal potential in this regard [6].

Chinese scientist F. Xiaolan analyzes the impact of the increase in the country's innovation potential on productivity. According to the results of his research, inward investment has a significant positive effect on the overall innovation capacity. But this effect will depend on the absorptive capacity of the

receiving national economy and the availability of innovation-providing factors [7].

Romanian scientists have justified the fact that foreign companies entering the country's national economy take regional characteristics into account in their investment strategies. According to their research, investors see Romanian regions as 2 separate economic regions. The availability of new markets, skilled workforce and infrastructure opportunities are cited as important factors in attracting investments in the first region. The second region attracted investors due to its low prices [8].

Research methodology

One of the most important factors determining the volume of domestic investments in the national economy is the expected net profit rate. Taking into account the inverse relationship between the interest rate and the amount of investment costs, there is a direct relationship between the dynamics of the expected net profit rate and investment costs. If the expected rate of return is higher than the interest rate, the investment is profitable, and conversely, if the interest rate is higher than the expected profit, the investment becomes unprofitable.

Analysis and results

Active attraction of direct investments, first of all foreign investments, to support the specialization of free economic zones in a certain field for the establishment of high-tech and localized modern enterprises that deeply process local mineral resources and produce competitive products with high added value. creates a basis for the development of industrial cooperation in them. Investments are the main factor of ensuring economic growth in Uzbekistan, and the analysis of investments made in the regions of the Republic is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

The volume of investments in the territories of the republic (in current prices, billion soums)

	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Republic of Uzbekistan	44810, 4	51232, 0	72155, 2	12423 1,3	18992 4,3
Republic of Karakalpakstan	6021,2	3778,3	2822,0	6757,8	8434,6
Andijan region	1956,5	2188,5	2986,0	4711,9	8183,7
Bukhara region	4075,9	5922,9	11613, 4	9610,9	9867,0
Jizzakh region	1304,9	1449,7	1788,2	3606,3	7919,3
Kashkadarya region	5894,7	7304,4	11175, 3	16518, 5	23525, 3
Navoi region	1809,1	2963,2	3977,9	10579, 5	17775, 3
Namangan region	2227,5	2824,5	3586,7	8158,1	12187, 0
Samarkand region	3237,2	3623,5	4384,2	7061,4	9798,6
Surkhandarya region	1843,6	2142,4	3551,0	7240,6	12232, 4
Syrdarya region	1083,3	1322,9	1628,0	2699,3	6129,2
Tashkent region	4428,1	4238,7	5938,4	11226, 9	16935, 1
Fergana region	2542,3	2643,6	2954,5	5539,1	9164,2
Khorezm region	1531,5	1560,5	2175,9	3013,8	5566,8
Tashkent city	6854,6	9268,9	13573, 7	26435, 7	41497, 9

As can be seen from the data of Table 1, in 2022, a total of 189924.3 billion will be transferred to our country. investments of soums have been made. Tashkent city (41497.9 billion soums), Kashkadarya region (23525.3 billion soums), Navoi region (17775.3 billion soums), Tashkent region (16935.1 billion soums) have the largest share of investments attracted to the economy. contributed, and in this regard, growth was observed in all regions.

Conclusions

The development of a long-term strategy for the development of the economy of Uzbekistan and its effective implementation require careful development of the medium-term investment policy strategy. In our opinion, in order to increase the efficiency of the use of internal financing sources and investment resources, it is necessary to implement the following measures:

- expanding their investment opportunities by strengthening the financial situation of enterprises based on increasing the volume of production and improving the quality of enterprises;

- to expand the investment potential of commercial banks and to increase the effectiveness of loans through the full use of market mechanisms in the banking system;

- organization of wide use of modern instruments of the financial market in the active involvement of public funds in production, etc. In order to improve the mechanism of attracting investments to the economy by introducing the use of modern market instruments, the following measures should be implemented:

- transferring the state's responsibility for attracting investments to the private sector by encouraging the wide use of market mechanism institutions such as investment agencies and engineering companies in actively attracting investments to the economy;

- taking into account the relative advantages of the regions, encouraging the attraction of investments by effectively using the existing prospective reserves,

unused or vacant land and production facilities for the development of secondary and tertiary processing of raw materials, labor-intensive and productive sectors, etc.

If the above measures are implemented, the domestic investment potential in the national economy will be effectively used and the volume of domestic investments will be increased.

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